

Smart Composite Materials

Performance Evaluation of Structural Behavior Monitoring using Smart Sensors

LIMS

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OUTLINE

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1 Background

2 Conductive repair materials

3 Material characteristics

4 Application to pothole repair

Background

» Importance of the Pothole Issue

- ✔ **Potholes are road damages** caused by repeated loads and environmental factors (e.g., freeze-thaw cycles, rainfall)
- ✔ Lead to vehicle damage, traffic accidents, and reduced road lifespan

Background

»» Necessity of Vehicle Load Detection

- ✔ **Pothole areas are structurally weak points** where vehicle loads concentrated
- ✔ Most conventional repair materials only fill the damage and **do not monitor the repaired area**
- ✔ Load self-sensing enables **early detection of re-damage and support timely maintenance decisions**

Conductive repair material

»» Development of Self-Sensing Repair Material

- ✔ Application of a **load-sensing** CNT/epoxy composite
- ✔ Development of a **CNT/epoxy-based repair material with fine aggregate**
- ✔ Composite material designed **to match the existing pavement**

CNT/Epoxxy composite

CNT

Conductive nanomaterials

Epoxxy

High strength

CNT/Epoxxy composite

Conductive composite

Conductive repair material

»» Development of Self-Sensing Repair Material

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Conductive repair material

CNT/Epoxy composite
Conductive composite

Aggregate

Conductive repair material
Self-sensing of load

Material characteristics

»» Effect of Aggregate on Electrical Conductivity

- Both samples showed **similar conductivity trends** with increasing CNT concentration
- Percolation threshold at 0.10 wt% & sharp increase up to 0.5 wt%
- Above 0.5 wt%, indicating network saturation

● Aggregate — Conductive path
 — CNT — Epoxy matrix

Material characteristics

»» Impact of Aggregate on Conductivity

- ⊙ Inclusion of aggregate caused a slight reduction in electrical conductivity.
- ⊙ The decrease became more noticeable at higher CNT contents.
- ⊙ Interference from aggregate, but CNTs still enhance conductivity.

CNT-Epoxy composite

Conductive repair material

Aggregate Conductive path
 CNT Epoxy matrix

Material characteristics

»»» Compression Test

Material characteristics

»» Effect of CNT Concentration on Mechanical Properties

- ☑ Fracture strain increased with CNT concentration
- ☑ Compressive strength increased at 0.25 wt%, then decreased at higher concentrations

Material characteristics

»» Effect of CNT Concentration on Workability and Strength

- ⊙ Increased CNT concentration raises composite viscosity → reduced workability
- ⊙ Decreased mechanical strength at higher CNT concentration

Material characteristics

»» Electrical Response Under Compression

- ☑ All samples showed a quasi-exponential decrease in resistance during compression
- ☑ Sensitivity decreased with higher CNT content due to denser conductive networks

Application to pothole repair

»» Application and Monitoring

- ✔ Applied the 0.25 wt% CNT repair material (highest compressive strength)
- ✔ Real-time electrical resistance was monitored using a multimeter
- ✔ Evaluated the material's self-sensing ability by detecting vehicle weight and traffic volume under real conditions

Pothole

Bottom electrode

Repair material

Top electrode

Application to pothole repair

»» Vehicle Load and Traffic Monitoring Test

☑ Detected vehicle weight and traffic flow using resistance changes

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Q&A

